

OVARIAN VEIN THROMBOSIS: A CASE REPORT

Sofia Aguilar^{*1}, Vera Cunha^{**}, João Colaço^{**}, Luísa Martins^{**}, Filomena Nunes^{**} and Mila Kayryakova[△]

^{*}Serviço de Ginecologia; Maternidade Dr. Alfredo da Costa – Centro Hospitalar Lisboa Central, Portugal., ^{**}Serviço de Ginecologia, Hospital de Cascais Dr. José de Almeida, Portugal., [△]Thoracic Surgery Clinic, Military Medical Academy, Sofia, Bulgaria.

ABSTRACT Ovarian vein thrombosis is rare, but potentially life-threatening. Mainly a post-partum complication, its timely diagnosis requires a high index of suspicion. Pelvic ultrasound is often used for initial evaluation, but contrast-enhanced computed tomography and magnetic resonance have superior diagnostic sensitivity. Anticoagulation plus antibiotics is the classical treatment; surgery is indicated for cases resistant to medical treatment or when the latter is contra-indicated. We present a case of ovarian vein thrombosis, complicating a post-late abortion endometritis, in a 43 years-old patient. Our purpose is to bring awareness to this condition, especially when fever resistant to antibiotherapy arises after childbirth or miscarriage.

KEYWORDS Ovarian vein thrombosis, Puerperium, Miscarriage

Introduction

Ovarian vein thrombosis (OVT) is a rare, but potentially serious entity.[1] Most commonly occurring in the context of pregnancy, the reported incidence is 1:600-1:2000 in the post-partum period and of 1:200 after a febrile abortion.[1],[2] It can also arise associated with endometritis, pelvic inflammatory disease, malignancy, pelvic surgery, inflammatory bowel disease and thrombophilias.[3],[4] Correct diagnosis requires a high suspicion index because clinically it can mimetize acute appendicitis, endometritis, pelvic inflammatory disease, adnexal torsion, broad ligament haematoma, pyelonephritis and hydronephrosis.[1],[5],[6]

The authors present a case of OVT diagnosed following post-abortion endometritis and a review of the literature regarding this thrombotic complication.

Methods

The study was conducted in the Department of Dermatovenereology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Hasanuddin and has obtained ethical approval from the Biomedical Research Ethics Commission in Hasanuddin University Medical School.

Case Report

A female patient, 43-year-old, with an irrelevant past medical history, gravida 3, para 3 (1 vaginal delivery e two caesarean sections, the three uncomplicated). Presents at the emergency room following an incomplete abortion at 15 weeks of pregnancy, diagnosed abroad, after which the patient travelled by plane for several hours to our country. She complained of light vaginal bleeding, denying other symptoms, abortion manoeuvres or expulsion of the foetus.

Abnormal signs during clinical observation were: a uterus fundus palpated at the level of the umbilicus and slight vaginal bleeding with a foul smell.

Transvaginal ultrasound showed a heterogeneous intrauterine image, suggestive of a retained placenta; the foetus was not visualized. Laboratory evaluation documented a slightly elevated C-reactive protein (CRP), with a normal leucogram (Table I).

Triple intravenous (IV) antibiotic therapy was initiated (consisting of ampicillin, gentamicin and clindamycin), and after that, manual removal of the placenta and uterine curettage under sonographic control were performed. The procedure was complicated by heavy uterine bleeding caused by uterus atony, leaving the patient hemodynamically unstable and with acute

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DOI:10.5455/IJMRCR.ovarian-vein-thrombosis

First Received: January 07, 2018

Accepted: August 14, 2018

Manuscript Associate Editor: Ivon Ribarova (BG)

¹Dr Ana Sofia Aguilar, Serviço de Ginecologia; Maternidade Dr. Alfredo da Costa – Centro Hospitalar Lisboa Central
E-mail: sofia6aguilar@gmail.com
Phone: 969609972 Mobile: 351 969609972

Figure.1.

anaemia (Hb=7,0g/dL). Since the condition was unresponsive to fluid reposition/resuscitation and uterotonic (oxytocin 40 IU IV, rectal misoprostol 800 µg and sulprostone 1000 µg IV), an intrauterine Bakri balloon was placed for uterine tamponade, which succeeds in controlling the bleeding. Five units of red cell concentrate and two units of fibrinogen were also administered. After these measures the patient's hemodynamic status and laboratory parameters became stable (Table 1). In the first post-procedure day, prophylactic low-molecular-weight heparin (LMWH) was initiated and the intrauterine balloon removed, following which the vaginal bleeding remained scarce. The patient was discharged three days after, clinically stable, and medicated with LMWH, iron supplementation and oral antibiotics.

Three days after, the patient returns to the emergency department, has developed a fever (39.1°C at admission). Vaginal bleeding remained light, but the foul smell persisted, and uterus subinvolution continued, although painless.

Ultrasound evaluation showed an intrauterine appearance suggestive of blood and clots, without evidence of retained placental fragments or uterine perforation. Blood workout documented an elevated white cell count/leucocytosis with neutrophilia and a rise in CRP. (Table 2).

The patient was readmitted to the hospital with the diagnosis of septic abortion, and a course of piperacillin/tazobactam was initiated. Despite this antibiotic regime, fever persisted, and an abdominopelvic contrast-enhanced computerized tomography was requested, which revealed a thrombus in the left ovarian vein, extending into the homolateral renal vein; the uterus showed signs of infection (Figure 1). LMWH dose was changed into a therapeutic one.

During the hospital, stay fever persisted. Cultural exams isolated *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in the urine and *Escherichia coli* in the blood; both were sensitive to Piperacillin/Tazobactam. Placenta histological diagnosis confirmed chorioamnionitis.

On the 11th hospitalization day, because of fever refractory to ongoing treatment and after exclusion of other infectious sites (through the performance of thoracic r-x-ray, echocardiogram,

Figure.1.2.

Figure.1.3.

Figure.1.4.

and repeated abdominopelvic computerized tomography), exploratory surgery was decided. The intraoperative assessment showed an enlarged uterus and left ovary and a thickened infundibulopelvic ligament consistent with an OVT. Rupture of a 2 cm segment of the uterine wall was also noted, suggesting dehiscence of C-section scar. A total hysterectomy and left salpingo-oophorectomy were performed, without complications.

Post-operative evolution was favourable, and fever resolved. The patient was discharged eight days after surgery, having by then completed a 14-day regimen of piperacillin/tazobactam. She was clinically well and continued anticoagulation at home. Further recovery was uneventful. Surgical specimen histopathological examination demonstrated inflammation of the uterus, fallopian tube and ovary.

Figure Legends

Figure 1: Findings from the 1st abdominopelvic contrast-enhanced CT-scan, showing an extensive thrombus in the left ovarian vein, reaching the homolateral renal vein (retroaórtica)

Figure 1.1: Axial plan showing the thrombus (arrow and dotted circle) extending to the left renal vein (arrowheads); kidney (K).

Figure 1.2: Axial plan showing the enlarged uterus with gas bubbles inside the endometrial cavity (arrow); CT-scan also identified hypodense focus in the uterine wall suggestive of collections in contiguity with the intrauterine content; this aspects are concordant with a recent surgical procedure or/versus a coexisting infection; one of the secondary signs of OVT is an enlarged uterus filled with fluid.

Figure 1.3: Coronal plan demonstrating an enlarged tubular structure (arrow) extending from de left the adnexal area, with a slightly enhanced wall and central hypodensity, where the thrombus is; uterus (U).

Figure 1.4: Coronal plan is showing the thrombus (arrow) progressing into the renal vein; multiplanar reconstructed coronal images are useful to evaluate thrombosis extent.

Days (Units)	1	1	2	3	3	4	4	6	Reference Ranges
Hb (g/dL)	12.1	7.0	8.1	6.7	7.9	7.4	8.5	8.8	12.0 - 16.0
Htc (%)	35	15	24.9	20.1	22.8	21.1	24.7	25.9	36.0 - 46.0
GB (x10 ⁹ /L)	9.6	-	7.1	13.7	13.7	9.4	9.8	10.1	4.0 - 10.0
N (x10 ⁹ /L)	76	-	76.5	90.2	90.2	87.0	86.1	75.9	40 - 75
PCR (mg/dL)	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	18.4	< 0.6

Table.1. Blood tests' results during the first hospital stay.

Days (Units)	1	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	17	19	20	Reference ranges
Hb (g/dL)	9.2	7.3	9.3	8.3	8.3	8.6	9.3	8.9	9.0	9.2	9.3	12.0 - 16.0
GB (x10 ⁹ /L)	13.6	14.7	12.2	10.0	10.2	10.9	11.7	17.1	9.1	8.6	8.6	4.0 - 10.0
N (x10 ⁹ /L)	81.4	88.4	85.0	81.1	75.4	81.7	77.5	89.0	73.9	71.4	67.5	40-75
PCR (mg/dL)	35.6	38.1	39.0	29.4	33.1	24.0	20.5	16.6	15.7	13.9	7.3	< 0.6

Table.2. Blood tests' results during the second hospital stay

Discussion

Pregnancy and the post-partum period are associated with a 5-fold increased risk of venous thromboembolism[7], due to a hypercoagulable state, endothelial injury e venous stasis[4],[6]. Pregnancy-related hypercoagulability persists until six weeks after delivery, reaching its peak on the 4th post-partum day.[6]

Ovarian veins (OV) are long vessels, with incompetent valves[6]. During pregnancy, their diameter triple[5], blood flow volume increases 60-fold, and their valve incompetence is bigger, leading to blood stasis.[3],[6] In the post-partum period, the sudden decrease in OV flow causes partial venous collapse, exacerbating the stasis.[5],[6]

Exogenous factors, like birth trauma or local inflammation with leucocyte infiltration occurring in endometritis[4], can cause injury to the surrounding vessels' intima layer[6], contributing to OVT.

OVT can develop until four weeks post-partum, but it usually occurs between the 7th and 10th puerperal days.[3],[6] Often with vague non-specific manifestations (malaise, abdominal discomfort) and a variable presentation, timely diagnosis requires a high level of suspicion.[3] The most frequent symptoms are fever unresponsive to antibiotic therapy, and acute lower abdominal pain; rarely, a mass can be palpated in the adnexal area.[3],[8] Some patients are asymptomatic, which is more common in malignancy-related cases[8]; in these circumstances, OVT is an incidental imagiologic finding, and the need to treat is yet to be established.[2],[8]

In up to 80-90%[5] of the times OVT develops in the right side[4], which has been attributed to various factors:

1. Pregnancy's physiologic dextrorotation of the uterus, causing compression of the right OV;[1],[5]
2. The acute angle between the right OV and the inferior vena cava (as opposed to the right angle between the left OV and the homolateral renal vein), making the right OV more prone to compression;[3]

	Placenta manual delivery and uterine curettage
	Transfusion of 2 units of red cell concentrates
	Transfusion of 1 unit of red cell concentrates
	Total hysterectomy + left salpingo-oophorectomy

Legend.I. Tables 1 and 2

3. - Post-partum antegrade blood flow in the right OV[3] , whereas in the left side it is retrograde;[1],[3] the latter prevents stasis and ascending infection[8] .
4. - Longer OV and with more incompetent valves on the right side, inducing blood stasis.[5],[7] Complications due to OVT, which are more frequent in the post-partum scenario[3] , include:
 5. - Thrombus progression into the renal veins or inferior vena cava[3],[5] ;
 6. - Pulmonary embolism (with a wide reported incidence, from close to 0% to 13%-33%1,[3],[4] ; associated mortality is approximately 4%-5%[1],[2]);
 7. - Acute ureteral obstruction (right ovarian vein crosses the ureter anteriorly at the level of L4)[4] ;
 8. - Ovarian infarction [5]
 9. - Sepsis[4]

Pelvic ultrasound is usually used for initial investigation/assessment and follow-up[1],[2] , because it is a simple and easily/readily accessible exam[9] , allowing for a quick exclusion of another diagnosis. Sonographically thrombosed OV appears as a tubular, serpiginous structure, hypoechoic or anechoic), localized in the affected adnexal area, adjacent to the ovarian artery, extending superiorly and with reduced or no flow on colour Doppler[1],[10] . Ultrasound limitations are due to its operator dependent performance/character[3] ; visibility impairment due to bowel gas interposition1,[3] and the inability to visualize the ovarian vein in all cases or its total extent[2]; additionally, OVT ultrasound image may be confused with appendicitis, hydroureter, lymphadenopathy, hydrosalpinx and inferior mesenteric vein thrombosis[3] . Sensitivity and specificity of colour-Doppler ultrasound for the diagnosis of OVT are estimated to be about 55.6% and 41.2% respectively[2].

OVT recognition by CT scan requires intravenous contrast administration, after which a filling defect in the affected OV is identified; the vein can also appear dilated and with an enhanced wall[9]. The classic CT finding is a dilated tubular retroperitoneal structure (corresponding to the OV), with wall enhancement, but contrast negative centrally in the thrombus zone, where it appears hypodense[7]. When seeing this image, CT-scan accuracy for the diagnosis of OVT is high, with a 77.8% - 100% sensibility and a 62.5 - 100% specificity [3,10].

Magnetic resonance angiography (MRA) has an equally high sensibility and specificity, close to 100%[1], but CT is the preferred imaging technique for OVT diagnosis because it is more cost-effective and obtainable.[3],[8] Magnetic resonance is usually reserved for cases where there is a high clinical suspicion but CT scanning is inconclusive or when the patient is allergic to the CT contrast agent[3] .

OVT spontaneous resolution is a possibility; however, as it is a life-threatening condition, anticoagulation is usually recommended.10 First-line treatment is pharmacological, consisting of anticoagulants and intravenous broad-spectrum antibiotics.[4],[5] Optimal duration/length of therapy and systemic use of antibiotics are not consensual.[3],[9] Some authors advocate a brief course of anticoagulants, reporting thrombus dissolution after 7-14 days; others argument that thrombosis persists

with short course treatments, recommending continuing anti-coagulants for 3-6 months, until imagiologic confirmation of resolution.[3]

If medical treatment is unsuccessful, severe or contra-indicated complications arise, other therapeutic options may be considered, including inferior vena cava filter, hysterectomy, thrombectomy, direct infusion of thrombolytic agents through venography or ligation of the inferior vena cava or ovarian vein.[4],[11]

There is a reported recurrence rate of approximately 3%. [5] Indication for thrombophilia investigation succeeding an OVT is controversial, as well as the need for thromboprophylaxis in the next pregnancy.[3],[4]

Our case is notable because of the more infrequent location of OVT in the left side, its level of extension into the renal vein and its occurrence after a late abortion. Uterine haemorrhage and endometritis that complicated the miscarriage most likely predisposed to the thromboembolic event. Also, medical treatment was ineffective, and the patient only got better after hysterectomy and left salpingo-oophorectomy.

The authors describe a case of OVT, because, even though rare, it is a diagnosis to consider, especially in the post-partum and post-abortion patient, presenting with fever refractory to antibiotherapy. Timely recognition and prompt treatment are crucial to avoid more severe outcomes.

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